

Historical Integration of Modern Urban Fabrics Using Place Making as a Tool

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ABSTRACT

Historic sites represent the identity of the city. The rapid urbanization and city-making process have led to the decay and neglect of historical sites. To recover historical sites from the decline process, a place-making approach is used as a tool. Complex areas, with a historical urban fabric symbolizing the city's origins and often linked to important historical buildings, form the center of historical cities in India. These areas serve as a central point of identity for the entire city and are often endowed with notable heritage buildings. One such historical location in India is the coastal stretch of Manapad. The town is referred to as "Little Jerusalem." The unplanned developments have tarnished the city's image by destroying its historical urban fabric and identity. The study's methodology is based on a field survey that uses a visual survey approach to collect data through the use of techniques like photography, diagrams, or maps, as well as the analysis of various literature to understand the components of the urban fabric, historical evolution, growth, and development. The study attempts to analyze the urban fabric of historic sites, identify factors affecting it, and suggest strategies and measures for integrating the historic vestiges into the modern urban fabric. The proposed strategies are some of the tools and techniques that could be adopted by urban designers, planners, and local planning authorities in improving the urban fabric of historic sites.

Keywords: Integration; Urban; Tools.

INTRODUCTION

The modern townscape is established by historic areas, that contribute to a city's memory, urban identity, and development. In recent times, the historical connection was ignored in the process of city-making. Due to the development pressure, the urban form is constantly changing and losing its identity and character. Change is inevitable. According to the needs of its inhabitants, urban spaces, streetscapes, and buildings change and evolve. The fabric of the

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past remains a challenge in many cities. This becomes a development block and, many times, it is being destroyed. So, it becomes a challenge in front of urban designers to conserve or preserve the vestiges and convert them into an opportunity. The rapid urbanization of cities resulted in a significant concern for historic vestiges recovery to incorporate it into the modern urban fabric. The study attempts to explore the notion of placemaking as an approach to developing and conserving historic vestiges.

Manapad is located in the southernmost region of the Indian subcontinent. It is a Fishing Community that is about 50 km far from Tuticorin, an ancient Indian port on the silk route. It is also called as “Little Jerusalem”. The history of Manapad dates back to the 14th century. The settlement was developed based on their occupation, which is fishing and pearl culture. It is Christian populated area with about 5,795 inhabitants that residing here.

The three main beaches are Solitary Beach, Melodious Sand Beach, and Blue Lagoon. Besides beaches, there are a number of interesting places to visit, including the St. Francis Xavier's Grotto (place where he used to live), Palm Leaf Society, Lighthouse, Manapad Point, and Wanderer's Trail.

RESEARCH ELABORATIONS

Since place-making is one of the methodologies for developing a system of urban places scattered over an urban region (Castello, 2006). Using the Place-making approach for historical sites various strategies and techniques are identified for Manapad such as: In terms of the linkage between the historic places and modern places, the street makes a separation between spaces. There are strong potentials to create more engagement between the historic places and modern places through street activities.

Activity of people are one of the key elements in creating effective places. A strong network of activities produces a population flow and a vibrant neighborhood. These activities include those that occur in the neighboring buildings as well as those that happen in public areas. Specific proper regulations regarding zoning, building byelaws, change of building use, have to be formulated for each of the zones to control changing physical fabric in core.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

At specific locations the entry points to the region along with parking areas have to be planned. ii The characteristic feature of the neighborhood that could be improved is the coexistence of old and new structures that are adjacent to one another. iii These issues could be addressed by adopting measures like identification of streets where pedestrianization could

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be promoted. iv The proper network of cycling facilities to be developed in historic area for the tourists. v The boundaries of the historic sites, e.g., walls and fences, could be redesigned to decrease the rigidness and welcome pedestrians that could facilitate the vigorous flow of people vi Manapad's history and collective memory appear to be important factors in shaping the city's identity. One attempt to connect with the past is the naming of streets throughout the city after notable or royal figures from the history.

CONCLUSIONS

Manapad has long history and its famous historic structures are located. It has historic urban fabric. These conditions reveal the high potentials for the region to strengthen its unique character by taking the historic places as valuable resources. Nowadays, Manapad's historic core is currently undergoing transformation. An increase in tourists is creating management issues like overcrowding, traffic congestion, parking issues, pressure on facilities, and much more. Also, it attracts more street vendors, which results in encroachment, among other things. Other modifications include the conversion of traditional structures to contemporary ones in residential areas, which results in loss of architectural character. Noticeable changes in built characteristics of the urban fabric due to the modern development.

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